

MODIFY: A Multi-Modal Anomaly Diagnosis Framework with Diffusion-Enhanced Adaptive Fusion in Microservices

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ABSTRACT

Microservice architecture has become the dominant paradigm for distributed systems due to its scalability and flexibility. However, its complex inter-service dependencies, and heterogeneous multimodal data pose significant challenges for anomaly diagnosis. Issues such as trace noise, weak cross-modal integration, and the separation of detection from localization often lead to limited diagnostic accuracy and poor real-time performance. To address these issues, we propose MODIFY, a multimodal anomaly diagnosis framework that leverages diffusion-enhanced adaptive feature fusion to detect and localize runtime performance- and availability-related anomalies in microservice systems. MODIFY models intra-service behavior and inter-service dependencies using logs, metrics, and traces. It incorporates a diffusion-based noise-resistant training strategy to improve robustness against trace-level noise and employs a multi-scale convolutional fusion module with a dynamic channel-adaptive mechanism for effective cross-modal feature integration. Experiments on two widely used microservice benchmarks demonstrate that MODIFY consistently outperforms state-of-the-art methods, achieving an average accuracy of 88.3% for anomaly detection and 84.7% for root cause localization. Our code is available at <https://github.com/WuFengXueYing/MODIFY>

1. Introduction

Microservice systems are composed of independently deployable services that communicate with each other, and have become a fundamental paradigm in modern distributed applications due to their loose coupling and high scalability. However, their dynamic, complex, and large-scale nature brings significant reliability challenges. An anomaly in a single microservice can propagate along invocation chains, potentially causing cascading failures that lead to economic losses, degraded user experience, and reputational damage [1, 2]. Timely anomaly detection is essential for early warning and containment, while accurate root cause localization enables prompt remediation, reduces recovery time, and helps prevent recurrence of similar failures. Therefore, developing an anomaly diagnosis system that integrates effective joint anomaly detection and root cause localization is critical for ensuring the reliability, availability, and resilience of microservice-based applications.

For microservice systems, multi-modal performance data—including traces, metrics, and logs—can be collected. Traces capture invocation chains and latency, logs record user activities and security events, and metrics measure real-time performance and resource usage, together providing comprehensive system observability. However, most existing anomaly diagnosis methods focus on single-modal data. For example, DeepLog [3] detects anomalies by learning sequential patterns from system logs, while DISTALYZER [4] uses log data to build causal models for root cause localization via critical path and slack analysis. Due to the

complexity of anomalies, relying on a single data source often leads to incomplete detection and inaccurate diagnosis, as different types of anomalies may manifest uniquely across logs, metrics, and traces. For instance, network congestion may cause noticeable delays in trace response times and changes in network-related metrics, but might not generate explicit anomalies in logs. Therefore, multi-modal anomaly diagnosis is essential to capture diverse anomaly patterns across data sources, enabling more accurate detection and precise root cause localization.

Several studies have explored multi-modal approaches to anomaly diagnosis. For example, DeepTraLog [5] integrates trace and log data into a graph structure and employs gated graph neural networks (GGNNs) with deep support vector data description (Deep SVDD) for joint anomaly detection, while DejaVu [6] fuses anomaly propagation patterns from service invocation chains with temporal metric features for interpretable fault localization. However, these methods treat anomaly detection and root cause localization as separate tasks, overlooking their inherent interdependence. In practice, effective microservice management requires these two tasks to operate collaboratively [7, 8], with accurate detection enabling precise and timely localization. In addition, multi-modal methods typically process each data modality separately and then fuse them. However, existing methods often ignore the presence of noise and fail to fully extract valuable information from performance data throughout the entire pipeline, which undermines accurate modeling of service dependencies and reduces diagnostic effectiveness.

In this paper, we define an anomaly as abnormal behaviors or signals in runtime observable data (i.e., logs, metrics, and traces) that deviate from normal patterns, such as latency anomalies, abnormal resource metrics, and intensity changes

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Figure 1: A motivating example of anomaly manifestation across traces, metrics, and logs in a social network microservice system.

of anomalous log events. Consider a typical user request scenario in a social networking application, as illustrated in Figure 1. When a user publishes a post, the request is sequentially propagated across multiple microservices along the invocation path: `nginx-web-server` → `compose-post-service` → `media-service` → `post-storage-service`. Suppose intermittent network congestion occurs between the `compose-post-service` and the `media-service`.

From the trace perspective, due to retry mechanisms and timeout configurations, the end-to-end request latency increases significantly, and the resulting latency time series exhibits pronounced bursty spikes, reflecting unstable execution behavior. Moreover, in real-world systems, trace data are often partially sampled to reduce system overhead and are generated only when requests occur, rather than being continuously collected at fixed intervals as metrics are. Consequently, under low-traffic conditions, trace data may suffer from sampling sparsity and fragmented missing segments, further introducing noise and incompleteness into the latency sequences.

From the metric perspective, only relatively mild variations can be observed, such as a slight increase in network throughput and a moderate rise in CPU utilization on the `media-service`. Importantly, these metric values remain within predefined Service Level Objectives (SLOs), and therefore do not independently trigger anomaly alerts. As a result, relying solely on metric signals would not provide sufficient evidence to identify the anomaly source.

From the log perspective, the system primarily records warning-level messages related to response delays, without producing explicit error logs. As a result, relying exclusively

on log patterns is insufficient for accurate root cause localization, especially when anomalies do not trigger clear failure messages or when warnings are only recorded in downstream services.

Overall, although trace data respond most directly to anomalies, they are also highly sensitive to noise introduced by retries, timeouts, and sparse sampling. Metrics provide continuous monitoring but often lack precise semantic interpretation, while logs contain explicit semantic information yet suffer from limited coverage. Therefore, each modality offers only a partial and biased view of the system state, and relying on any single modality is insufficient to achieve reliable and accurate anomaly diagnosis.

There are two key challenges in extracting valuable information from data. First, in single-modal processing, many anomaly diagnosis methods fail to fully utilize available data, particularly trace data. Call chains are often affected by various forms of noise, and existing methods frequently overlook how such noise can compromise the accurate modeling of microservice invocation dependencies. Second, for multi-modal data fusion, most existing methods rely on simplistic fusion strategies such as shallow linear techniques like concatenation or weighted averaging, without adaptive weight adjustment, which fails to fully exploit multi-modal data. This lack of dynamic and context-aware integration leads to the loss of cross-modal semantic associations and weakens anomaly detection performance.

To address these challenges and enhance anomaly diagnosis performance for ensuring microservice reliability, we propose MODIFY, a supervised learning-based

Multi-modal anomaly Diagnosis framework with diffusion-enhanced adaptive Fusion. Specifically, we extract single-modal features from logs, metrics, and diffusion-enhanced traces. The diffusion mechanism injects controllable noise during training and learns denoising objectives, thereby improving the model's robustness to noisy and incomplete trace data commonly observed in microservice systems. These single-modal features are then integrated through a multi-scale channel-adaptive convolutional gated fusion module, which models multimodal features at different resolutions through multi-scale convolutions while adaptively weighting features across modalities, enabling effective cross-modal representation learning. In parallel, we construct a microservice invocation dependency graph from historical call chains to explicitly model inter-service interactions. By combining this graph structure with the fused multimodal features, we employ a Graph Attention Network (GAT) to embed and aggregate feature information at the microservice node level, where the attention mechanism learns the relative importance of neighboring services in anomaly propagation. Finally, the aggregated embeddings are fed into the anomaly detector and the root cause localizer, which are jointly trained under the supervision of ground-truth root cause labels to perform anomaly detection and service-level root cause diagnosis. Our contributions can be summarized as follows:

- 1) We introduce a novel diffusion-based noise-resilient feature extraction encoder (DNR-FE) specifically designed for trace data, directly addressing the challenges of noise and instability in microservice call chains. By actively injecting and removing noise during training, our approach significantly enhances the robustness of anomaly propagation modeling and provides a more reliable feature foundation for diagnosis.
- 2) We design an adaptive multi-modal fusion framework named MSCA-CGFM, which enables dynamic integration and semantic association across heterogeneous data sources. Our multi-scale channel-adaptive fusion mechanism dynamically adjusts feature weights according to context, fully exploiting the complementarity of multi-source data and overcoming the limitations of conventional linear fusion strategies.
- 3) We propose MODIFY, a unified framework for multi-modal anomaly diagnosis that captures dependencies within microservices and across invocation chains. Once anomalies are detected from the fused representation, the localizer reuses the same features for root cause localization, eliminating redundant processing.
- 4) We conduct extensive experiments on two benchmark datasets, demonstrating that MODIFY outperforms all comparative methods in anomaly diagnosis. Additional ablation studies, hyperparameter sensitivity tests, convergence analysis, and time cost evaluation further validate its effectiveness from multiple perspectives.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows: Section 2 reviews related work. Section 3 presents the overall architecture of the proposed model. Section 4 details the experimental setup and results. Finally, Section 5 concludes the paper and discusses potential directions for future research.

2. Related Work

Prior studies on anomaly diagnosis have extensively explored single-modal data, as such approaches offer relatively low computational overhead, clearer modeling assumptions, and better interpretability. These methods have laid important foundations for understanding abnormal system behaviors from individual observability sources. With the increasing complexity of microservice systems and recent advances in multimodal representation learning and fusion techniques, some recent studies have started to leverage multiple data modalities to achieve more comprehensive and reliable anomaly diagnosis. In this section, we review representative anomaly diagnosis methods from different observability perspectives and discuss how multimodal approaches complement single-modal methods by capturing richer system behaviors.

2.1. Abnormal Diagnosis Based on single-modal Data

Log-Based: Logs record event information during microservice system runtime, encompassing system data, user behaviors, and network operations. As logs capture critical events and state transitions in system execution, parsing log templates and parameters extracts structured information that provides direct evidence for analyzing system behaviors, detecting anomalous patterns, and localizing fault origins.

Early log-based approaches mainly focus on modeling normal execution patterns of log sequences. For example, DeepLog [3] is a classical log-index-based method, it performs anomaly detection by learning the sequential patterns of normal log sequences using an LSTM model and identifying anomalies based on deviations in the predicted probability of the next log entry. To address the issue of log instability caused by evolving logging statements and noise, LogRobust [9] incorporates semantic vectorization and attention-based sequence modeling, thereby enhancing the robustness of anomaly detection in real-world industrial scenarios. LogM [10] offers unsupervised and supervised fault diagnosis techniques: Its unsupervised method identifies root causes by computing log cosine similarity, while the supervised approach uses a Siamese LSTM network for similarity calculation—both establishing mappings from logs to root causes. Additionally, LogM integrates CNNs and attention-based Bi-LSTM to capture temporal dynamics in log sequences for detecting abnormal patterns and supporting failure prediction.

Metric-Based: Metrics reflect system resource utilization and performance, offering granular insights into runtime states [11]. These quantitative data support real-time monitoring and historical analysis. By modeling correlations

Table 1

Summary of representative anomaly diagnosis methods. Data specifies the input data type, where L denotes logs, M denotes metrics, T denotes traces, Theory refers to the theoretical foundation or analytical principle applied in each method. Here, R stands for rule-based approaches, ML represents machine learning-based methods, and DL indicates deep learning-based techniques. Supervision shows the type of learning employed: Sup for supervised learning, Unsup for unsupervised learning, Key Features briefly summarizes the core mechanisms or innovations of each approach.

Category	Approach	Year	Data	Theory	Supervision	Key Features
Based on Single-modal Data	DeepLog	2017	L	DL	Unsup	Log Sequence Modeling + LSTM
	LogRobust	2019	L	DL	Sup	Attention-LSTM + TF-IDF
	LogM	2021	L	DL	Sup/Unsup	CNN + Bi-LSTM + TF-IDF
	CloudRanger	2018	M	R	Unsup	PC Algorithm + Random Walk
	MonitorRank	2019	M	R/ML	Unsup	Invocation Graph + Random Walk
	DyCause	2021	M	R	Unsup	Crowdsourcing Graph Fusing + BFS
	DejaVu	2022	M	DL	Sup	FDG + GNN
	TraceAnomaly	2020	T	DL	Unsup	VAE + Posterior Flow
Based on Multimodal Data	MultimodalTrace	2022	T	DL	Unsup	Span Structure + Multimodal LSTM
	DeepTraLog	2022	L/T	DL	Sup	GGNNs + Deep SVDD
	MULAN	2024	L/M	DL	Unsup	Contrastive Learning + GraphSage
	TraceGra	2023	M/T	DL	Sup	GNN + Temporal Encoder-Decoder
	MicroIRC	2024	M/T	DL	Sup	Temporal Topology + Random Walk
	PDiagnose	2021	L/M/T	ML	Unsup	Anomaly Queue + Voting Mechanism
	Groot	2021	L/M/T	ML	Unsup	Event Causal Graph + PageRank
	Eadro	2023	L/M/T	DL	Sup	Multi-modal Fused Representation + GAT
	Nezha	2023	L/M/T	R/ML	Unsup	Unified Event Graph + Structural Deviation Analysis
	ART	2024	L/M/T	DL	Unsup	Self-supervised Learning + Transformer Encoder
AMuLSys	2025	L/M/T	DL	Sup	Hybrid Graph + Contrastive Learning	

among metrics, abnormal patterns can be effectively identified and fault origins localized, thereby enhancing system observability and reliability.

MonitorRank [12] leverages statistical similarity to compute similarity patterns between time-series metrics and performs personalized random walks on the service call graph to infer root causes from metric data. By combining metric similarity with call graph constraints, MonitorRank generates a ranked list of candidate root cause instances for post-anomaly diagnosis without requiring labeled data. Beyond correlation-based reasoning, some approaches explicitly infer causal relationships from metrics. CloudRanger [13] applies the PC algorithm to construct dynamic causal graphs from performance metrics, and subsequently utilizes random walk strategies over the inferred causal structures to identify root cause microservice instances. To address the challenges posed by complex dependency structures and anomaly propagation, DyCause [14] introduces a multi-stage analysis framework. It derives local dependency

graphs using sliding windows, fuses them through crowdsourced graph optimization, and traces anomaly propagation paths via reverse breadth-first search to rank candidate root causes. More advanced methods further consider the heterogeneity of fault types. DejaVu [6] tackles multi-type fault coupling by designing fault-specific feature extractors and projecting heterogeneous faults into unified representation spaces. Structural information from Failure Dependency Graphs (FDGs) is aggregated through attention mechanisms, and Graph Neural Networks (GNNs) are employed to jointly localize root cause instances and identify fault categories.

Trace-Based: Trace data comprehensively records the execution paths of requests across a system and invocation relationships between services, providing detailed call chain information for anomaly diagnosis. By analyzing tracing data, the execution status of requests at each service node—including abnormal manifestations such as latency and errors—can be clearly observed, enabling precise localization of faults within specific service segments.

An initial line of work focuses on exploiting the rich structural and temporal information embedded in tracing data. MultimodalTrace [15] treats traces as composite sequences that contain both structural execution patterns and response-time measurements. By adopting a multimodal LSTM architecture to jointly encode call-path structures and latency signals, it improves anomaly detection for complex scenarios involving concurrent or dependent service invocations that are difficult to characterize using a single trace modality. Subsequently, generative modeling techniques were introduced to characterize normal trace behaviors. TraceAnomaly [16] employs a Variational Autoencoder (VAE) to learn the latent distribution of normal microservice traces, encompassing both invocation paths and performance features. Deviations from this learned distribution are quantified through reconstruction errors, which serve as indicators of anomalous executions that diverge from expected trace patterns.

2.2. Anomaly Diagnosis Based on Multimodal Data

Multimodal methods provide a more comprehensive reflection of system operational states by integrating data from diverse sources—such as logs, metrics, traces, events, and topology—thereby identifying potential issues across different layers and enabling diagnosis of a broader range of failure types with finer-grained root cause localization. Current fault diagnosis technologies primarily focus on the observability of microservice systems, where logs, metrics, and traces constitute the three pillars of observability. Consequently, multimodal anomaly diagnosis should incorporate at least two of these three data types.

For instance, DeepTraLog[5] unifies trace and log data into a graph structure, employing GGNNs combined with Deep SVDD for joint model training to detect anomalies. TraceGra [17] models tracing data as dependency graphs that integrate invocation relationships with container-level performance metrics. By combining Graph Neural Networks (GNNs) for structural dependency learning with LSTM-based autoencoders for temporal modeling, TraceGra enables fine-grained fault localization while accounting for anomaly propagation across service dependencies. MicroIRC [18] performs instance-level root cause localization by modeling multidimensional metric time series with graph neural networks and ranking faulty instances via personalized random walks on a dynamically constructed service topology. MULAN[19] utilizes GraphSage to simultaneously extract instance-specific representations and joint invariant representations, fusing logs and metrics through contrastive learning to form unified log-metric embeddings. It further constructs learnable causal graphs for each representation type, integrates decoder results via a KPI-aware attention module, and ultimately localizes root causes via random walks. In contrast to MULAN, ART[20] emphasizes universal representation learning and multi-task compatibility, standardizing multimodal data into temporal formats for self-supervised pre-training; reconstruction errors computed

during training serve anomaly signals for downstream diagnosis tasks. PDiagnose [21] comprehensively leverages logs, metrics, and traces: It detects anomalous metrics via KDE(Kernel Density Estimation) and weighted moving averages, queues anomalies for feature extraction, reports suspicious microservices by comparing request durations against thresholds, and finally confirms root cause components through dual validation using abnormal metric ratios and log analysis. Groot [22] constructs service dependency graphs from traces and logs, integrating performance metrics, status logs, and developer activities to generate events. Causal rules translate these into causal graphs, where triggered alerts activate the GrootRank algorithm to output root cause lists. Eadro [23] processes logs (parsed into template events with temporal intensity modeling), metrics, and trace latencies (capturing temporal and cross-sequence dependencies) before fusing these features with trace-derived dependency graphs. This fused representation is fed into a graph attention network for system state learning, enabling normality evaluation and root cause ranking. In contrast, to achieve higher interpretability and more fine-grained root cause analysis, Nezha [24] performs structural deviation analysis to localize root causes at granular levels, such as specific code regions or resource types. Specifically, it transforms multimodal data into a unified event representation and constructs an event graph for each request to capture the execution structure. By mining frequent event patterns and comparing their support between normal and failure phases, it precisely identifies anomalies. AMuLSys [25] further advances multimodal anomaly analysis by jointly modeling logs, metrics, and traces through heterogeneous graph representations and cross-modal attention mechanisms. By integrating trace-metric dependency graphs with log semantic graphs and enhancing learning via multimodal data augmentation.

Summary Overall, the current research on microservice anomaly diagnosis shows that although single-modal approaches have become relatively mature, their diagnostic accuracy and coverage remain limited due to the complexity and diversity of anomalies. Multi-modal approaches, by integrating data such as logs, metrics, and traces, can provide a more comprehensive diagnostic perspective and identify anomalies that single-modal methods fail to detect. However, existing multi-modal methods still suffer from several limitations. For example, Eadro adopts a relatively coarse gated connection strategy for multi-modal feature fusion; this approach neither explicitly addresses trace-level noise and sparsity issues nor provides a context-aware, multi-scale adaptive fusion mechanism. Similarly, AMuLSys focuses on multi-modal anomaly detection by constructing hybrid graph representations, while explicitly treating root cause analysis as future work rather than offering a unified detection-localization diagnostic pipeline.

To address these challenges, MODIFy proposes a unified multi-modal anomaly diagnosis framework that jointly performs anomaly detection and root cause localization.

Figure 2: The architecture of MODIFY

By integrating logs, metrics, and traces, MODIFY models both intra-service behaviors and inter-service dependencies, and introduces a diffusion-based noise-resilient feature encoder to mitigate the impact of trace noise. In addition, the framework employs a multi-scale channel-adaptive gated convolution fusion module to achieve dynamic and context-aware multi-modal integration. By sharing representations between detection and localization tasks, MODIFY reduces redundant computation and avoids the noise amplification problem commonly observed in traditional serial diagnostic pipelines.

3. Preliminary

3.1. Diffusion-based Noise Modeling

Observability data in production systems inevitably contain noise due to logging redundancy, metric fluctuation, and trace sampling. Robust representation learning therefore requires effective noise handling.

Diffusion models [26] were originally proposed as generative probabilistic models that learn data distributions by gradually adding noise and then reversing the process to recover clean samples. From a representation learning perspective, diffusion-based modeling can be viewed as a progressive denoising mechanism, where structured information is preserved while stochastic noise is suppressed.

3.2. Multi-scale Convolutional Gating

Microservice anomalies may manifest at different temporal resolutions. Some faults cause abrupt metric spikes, while others induce gradual degradation patterns. Capturing such diverse temporal characteristics requires multi-scale modeling.

Multi-scale convolution applies convolutional filters with different receptive fields to capture short-term and long-term dependencies simultaneously. To further improve

feature selectivity, a gating mechanism is introduced to adaptively weight features extracted at different scales [27]. Gating enables the model to dynamically emphasize informative temporal patterns while suppressing irrelevant fluctuations.

This design enhances temporal sensitivity and improves anomaly discriminability across heterogeneous scenarios.

3.3. Graph Attention Networks for Dependency Modeling

Microservice systems naturally form dynamic service invocation graphs. Since anomalies propagate along dependency paths, modeling inter-service relationships is crucial for root cause localization.

Graph Neural Networks [28] (GNNs) extend deep learning to graph-structured data by aggregating neighborhood information. Among them, Graph Attention Networks [29] (GATs) introduce attention mechanisms to assign learnable importance weights to neighboring nodes. This allows the model to differentiate critical dependencies from weak or noisy connections.

By combining structural topology with learned attention weights, GATs provide a principled way to model anomaly propagation patterns and enhance interpretability in root cause inference.

4. Methodology

In this section, we detail the implementation of MODIFY. As illustrated in Figure 2, the framework comprises three main stages. The first stage is single-modal feature extraction, where each data source is processed using appropriate methods to generate aligned features: log data is transformed into embeddings via a Hawkes process, metric data is encoded with a Transformer Encoder to capture global

dependencies, and trace data is enhanced using diffusion-based noise-resilient feature extraction encoder (DNR-FE). Additionally, the microservice call dependency graph is extracted from the traces.

The second stage involves multi-modal feature fusion. The extracted features are fed into the Multi-scale adaptive convolutional gated fusion module (MSCA-CGFM) for multi-scale, channel-adaptive convolutional fusion. The resulting representations, together with the dependency graph, are then passed to a graph attention network to learn a global feature representation.

In the third stage, MODIFY performs joint anomaly detection and root cause localization in a supervised learning manner. Specifically, the model first leverages the global representation obtained from the graph attention network and applies an anomaly detector to perform binary classification and identify suspicious anomalous microservices. Based on this, a list of candidate services is constructed, and the root cause localizer is then trained using the provided ground-truth root cause annotations to pinpoint the specific faulty microservice. Through this joint supervision, the model learns to accurately detect anomalous system states and precisely localize the corresponding faulty microservices.

4.1. Single-Modal Feature Extraction

A) Log Feature Extraction Logs capture a wide range of events generated during microservice system operation, such as system activities, user interactions, and network-related business processes. Effectively extracting meaningful information from these logs is crucial. To process the logs, we first employ the Drain3 algorithm [30] to parse unstructured log messages into structured templates, facilitating downstream analysis. Subsequently, we utilize the Hawkes process [31]—a self-exciting point process—to model the temporal dynamics of event occurrences. Unlike conventional approaches that analyze the semantic content of logs, the Hawkes process models the underlying patterns of log occurrences. Specifically, when and at what frequency log events happen. This is critical because in microservice environments, certain anomalies may not generate explicit "Error" logs, but can alter the frequency or patterns of normal events. The Hawkes process captures such "self-exciting" behavioral shifts, where earlier events trigger subsequent ones, thereby revealing subtle anomaly-induced dependencies. Within each time window, we organize log events as sequences, where each event is characterized by its template type and timestamp. The Hawkes process leverages an exponential decay kernel to estimate the influence of historical events on the probability of future occurrences. We represent the expected occurrence rates of different event types in a time window using an intensity vector $\Lambda = [\lambda_1^*, \dots, \lambda_L^*]$, where λ_l^* denotes the intensity for event type l . The intensity function is defined as:

$$\lambda_l^*(t) = \mu_l(t) + \sum_{\tau < t} \phi_l(t - \tau) \quad (1)$$

where μ_l is the base intensity, which is initialized to 0.2 for all event types and learned from data via maximum

Figure 3: Trace Diffusion Trunk

likelihood estimation, and $\phi_l(\cdot) = \alpha_l \beta \exp(-\beta t)|_{t>0}$, with $\alpha_1 \dots \alpha_L$ as a learnable parameters and β as a predefined hyperparameter. Finally, the intensity vector Λ is passed through a fully connected layer with hidden size E^L , producing the embedded log representation F^L .

B) Transformer-Based Metric Feature Extraction To obtain meaningful performance metrics from the running system, we first normalize and segment the raw monitoring data into sequential windows, forming a multi-dimensional time-series matrix suitable for model input. To address discrepancies caused by different measurement units, we apply Z-score normalization to each metric $m_j \in M$, where M is the set of all metrics collected from N microservice nodes. The observation period is then divided into K consecutive, fixed-length time windows $W = \{(s_1, e_1), (s_2, e_2), \dots, (s_K, e_K)\}$, resulting in a four-dimensional tensor $\mathcal{X} \in \mathbb{R}^{K \times N \times T \times M}$. For high-level semantic feature extraction from the time-series data, we employ a Transformer encoder, which utilizes multi-head self-attention to model global temporal dependencies and outputs the embedded metric representation F^M .

C) Diffusion-Enhanced Trace Feature Extraction From the raw trace data collected from multiple requests, we first extract the call chains and aggregate the latency values for each microservice within fixed time intervals. By calculating the average latency in each window, we construct a univariate time series for every service, resulting in a latency matrix that reflects temporal variations across all services. However, trace data typically exhibits high sparsity and a long-tail distribution—most requests have low latency, while a minority experience significant spikes. This leads to latency series with zero-padding in inactive periods and abrupt outliers due to issues like timeout retries [32]. Such irregularities make diffusion models particularly suitable, as they can learn robust temporal patterns by progressively adding and removing noise. Therefore, before extracting downstream features, we apply DNR-FE to enhance the preprocessed trace data using diffusion-based feature augmentation, effectively reducing the impact of noise.

As illustrated in Figure 3, to enable the model to adapt to varying noise levels, we randomly select a diffusion timestep for each instance in the batch, with each timestep corresponding to a specific noise intensity. Gaussian noise is injected into the trace features to generate noisy samples, formulated as:

$$F^\tau = \sqrt{\bar{\alpha}_t} \cdot F_0^\tau + \sqrt{1 - \bar{\alpha}_t} \cdot \epsilon \quad (2)$$

Here, F_0^τ denotes the original trace feature, ϵ represents Gaussian noise, and $\bar{\alpha}_t$ is the cumulative retention factor that controls the proportion of original features and noise during the forward diffusion process. These noisy samples are then processed by a denoising network composed of stacked 1D convolutions and ReLU activations, allowing the model to learn and suppress typical noise patterns present in trace data.

After denoising, we calculate the average latency for each microservice within fixed time windows, forming a univariate time series per service. These sequences are subsequently fed into a Transformer encoder, which extracts high-level temporal representations from the latency traces for downstream tasks.

We also applied diffusion-based feature enhancement to log data and service metrics, but observed suboptimal results. Our analysis indicates that log data, being discrete text sequences, exhibit noise patterns and feature distributions distinct from continuous trace latency, thereby reducing the effectiveness of diffusion. Similarly, service metrics such as CPU utilization demonstrate low and predictable variability, as noted in prior work[33]. Consequently, noise injection through diffusion leads to undesirable perturbations and distributional shifts that degrade feature quality. In contrast, trace latency, which is subject to external factors such as network congestion, benefits more significantly from diffusion in mitigating noise.

4.2. Multi-modal feature fusion

(1) Modal alignment.

To ensure precise temporal alignment across heterogeneous modalities with different sampling granularities, we adopt a unified sliding-window aggregation strategy. Specifically, all timestamps from logs, metrics, and traces are first normalized onto a global timeline to establish a consistent temporal reference. Considering that metrics are typically collected at fixed intervals (e.g., every 5–15 seconds), whereas traces are event-driven and recorded at millisecond granularity, we define a fixed-length sliding window of 6 seconds as the fundamental temporal unit for synchronization. Within each window, trace spans falling into the interval are aggregated by computing the average latency for each microservice, thereby generating a window-level latency representation. Metric data are resampled when necessary to align with the same window boundaries, ensuring consistent temporal segmentation. Meanwhile, log events occurring within the window are grouped together, and their Hawkes-process-based intensity vectors are computed to capture temporal dynamics. Through this window-based aggregation and resampling mechanism, all modalities are mapped into temporally aligned feature representations, guaranteeing temporal consistency before being fed into the subsequent multimodal fusion framework.

Following this alignment, the embedding features of logs, metrics, and diffusion-enhanced traces are concatenated along the channel dimension, resulting in a fused representation $[F^\mathcal{L} \parallel F^\mathcal{M} \parallel F^\mathcal{T}]$ for each microservice.

Furthermore, we extract structural dependencies among microservices by analyzing historical invocation traces. Specifically, we construct a directed call dependency graph $G = \{V, E\}$, where V denotes the set of microservice nodes and E represents the directed edges, each capturing the invocation direction from one service to another. To build this graph, we parse distributed traces by extracting the microservice ID and name associated with each span (i.e., a single operation or request segment in a distributed trace), leveraging parent–child relationships (or span links) to infer caller–callee pairs, and utilizing timestamps and durations for temporal aggregation and latency sequence construction. The concatenated feature vector $[F^\mathcal{L} \parallel F^\mathcal{M} \parallel F^\mathcal{T}]$, combined with the topology of G , provides downstream graph-based models with comprehensive inputs to effectively capture both temporal dynamics and relational patterns for system behavior analysis.

(2) Multi-scale Channel-adaptive Convolutional Gated Feature Fusion.

For the concatenated representation $[F^\mathcal{L} \parallel F^\mathcal{M} \parallel F^\mathcal{T}]$, we introduce an enhanced Convolutional-Gated Linear Unit (CGLU) to facilitate effective fusion of multi-modal features. Our design incorporates a multi-scale convolutional structure, which captures dependencies at different scales, thereby significantly enriching the diversity of the extracted features. Additionally, a channel-adaptive mechanism is integrated to dynamically recalibrate feature channels based on global context, enabling more informative fusion. The resulting architecture, termed the Multi-Scale Channel-Adaptive Convolutional Gated Fusion Module (MSCA-CGFM) and depicted in Figure 4, serves as a powerful component for integrating multi-modal representations in microservices. Specifically, the MSCA-CGFM can be decomposed into the following two components.

-Multi-scale Convolutional Gated Linear Unit (CGLU).

Traditional Convolutional-Gated Linear Unit (CGLU) modules improve feature representation by integrating depthwise convolution and a gating mechanism to regulate information flow selectively. Nevertheless, their reliance on a fixed 3×3 kernel size constrains the receptive field and hinders the model’s capacity to capture multi-scale contextual information. To overcome this limitation, we introduce a multi-scale CGLU architecture that captures fused features across varying scales.

Following the standard CGLU design, we first concatenate the multi-modal representations $[F^\mathcal{L} \parallel F^\mathcal{M} \parallel F^\mathcal{T}]$ and project them into a lower-dimensional space through a fully connected layer. The resulting features are then transformed linearly and divided along the last dimension into two branches: a feature transformation branch denoted as H^1 and a gating branch denoted as H^2 , formalized as:

$$[H^1, H^2] = \text{split} \left(W_f \left[F^\mathcal{L} \parallel F^\mathcal{M} \parallel F^\mathcal{T} \right] \right) \quad (3)$$

The branch H^1 is processed through a nonlinear transformation to extract informative features, while H^2 produces a gating control signal via a sigmoid activation $\sigma(H^2) \in (0, 1)$,

Figure 4: The structure of MSCA-CGFM

which modulates H^1 through an element-wise Hadamard product. However, in the original CGLU framework, H^1 is processed solely by a single 3×3 convolution, potentially limiting its capacity to capture broader contextual dependencies. To address this limitation, we introduce a multi-scale convolutional gating mechanism that processes H^1 using parallel 3×3 and 5×5 depthwise separable convolutions, yielding fused features H_{dw}^1 . This multi-scale design combines receptive fields of varying sizes, enabling the model to capture interactions at different scales, thereby enriching feature diversity. The contributions of each scale are governed by learnable weights w_1 and w_2 (where $w_1 + w_2 = 1$), which are updated during training. The resulting feature representation preserves both contextual information and fine-grained details, as expressed by:

$$H_{dw}^1 = w_1 \cdot DWConv_{3 \times 3}(H^1) + w_2 \cdot DWConv_{5 \times 5}(H^1) \quad (4)$$

The output of the Hadamard product ($H_{dw}^1 \odot \sigma(H^2)$) is then fed into a Squeeze-and-Excitation (SE) block. Within this module, channel attention is applied to adaptively enhance features, resulting in the final fused multi-modal representation.

-Channel Adaptive Mechanism. Although the multi-scale CGLU module effectively modulates information flow, it fails to explicitly consider the relative importance of individual channels. To overcome this limitation, we integrate a lightweight Squeeze-and-Excitation (SE) attention mechanism, which explicitly models global contextual relationships and enables adaptive feature refinement along the channel dimension. Specifically, global average pooling is first applied to compress spatial information from each channel into a compact descriptor. This is then passed through a fully connected layer for dimensionality reduction and nonlinear activation. Subsequently, a second fully connected layer, followed by a sigmoid activation, produces a set of channel-wise attention weights $s_c \in (0, 1)$. These weights are used to dynamically recalibrate the original features, enhancing informative channels while suppressing less relevant ones. The channel weighting process is formally defined

as:

$$s_c = \sigma \left(W_2 \cdot \text{ReLU} \left(W_1 \cdot \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N h_i \right) \right) \quad (5)$$

Here, h_i denotes the feature vector of the i -th channel, and σ is the sigmoid activation function.

Eventually, this process synthesizes the final fused multi-modal representation H^S . The comprehensive fusion procedure, which integrates both convolutional gating and channel attention mechanisms, is formally expressed as:

$$H^S = SE(H_{dw}^1 \odot \sigma(H^2)) \quad (6)$$

(3) Graph Attention Network Modeling.

Following the comprehensive fusion of multi-modal features for each microservice, we integrate the global structural information encapsulated by the directed graph G . The fused node features are embedded into the call dependency graph and processed using a Graph Attention Network (GAT), which learns dependency-aware representations of the microservice system. This allows the model to adaptively determine the significance of neighboring nodes, thereby prioritizing microservices that display anomalous behavior. Specifically, we employ stacked GATv2Conv layers to dynamically learn attention weights between nodes. The feature update for node i at the $(l+1)$ -th layer is formulated as:

$$h_i^{(l+1)} = \sigma \left(\frac{1}{K} \sum_{k=1}^K \sum_{j \in \mathcal{N}(i)} \alpha_{ij}^{(k)} W^{(k)} h_j^{(l)} \right) \quad (7)$$

where K denotes the number of attention heads (default: 4), $\mathcal{N}(i)$ represents the set of neighboring nodes of i , $\alpha_{ij}^{(k)}$ is the attention coefficient from node j to node i in the k -th head, W is the attention coefficient from node j to node j in the k -th head, $W^{(k)}$ denotes a learnable weight matrix, and $h_j^{(l)}$ refers to the feature representation of node j at the l -th layer.

To improve training efficiency, we utilize only a single GATv2Conv layer. The multi-head outputs are compressed

along the channel dimension via max pooling, where the kernel size is set equal to the number of attention heads. This operation reduces redundancy in the multi-head attention mechanism while retaining essential feature information. Finally, a global attention aggregation is applied to all node representations, yielding the overall system state representation H_G :

$$H_G = \sum_{i=1}^N \alpha_i h_i \quad (8)$$

Here, α_i represents the learned attention weight of node i , h_i is its feature vector, and N is the total number of nodes in the graph.

4.3. Joint Detection and Root Cause Localization

To overcome the inherent inefficiency and noise sensitivity of traditional two-stage anomaly diagnosis frameworks, we propose a multi-task joint learning architecture. The architecture adopts a dual-branch design that simultaneously performs anomaly detection and root cause localization. This unified framework consists of two core components—a detector and a localizer—both implemented with fully connected layers and trained in a supervised manner.

Specifically, in the preceding stage, we employ a Graph Attention Network to aggregate the feature representations of all nodes in the service invocation dependency graph into a graph-level embedding that represents the global system state. This shared representation is then fed into two task-specific branches. The anomaly detector performs binary classification with an output dimension of 2, indicating whether the system state is anomalous, while the root cause localizer outputs a probability distribution over all nodes, with the output dimension equal to the number of nodes and a softmax activation function used to estimate the fault probability of each node.

Both the anomaly detector and the root cause localizer are optimized using cross-entropy loss functions. During inference, the predicted node fault probabilities are sorted in descending order to generate a ranked list of candidate root cause nodes. For samples detected as anomalous, the predicted root cause ranking is compared with the ground-truth root cause labels to determine the final root cause.

The detection loss is defined as the binary cross-entropy:

$$\mathfrak{L}_1 = \sum_{i=1}^N \left[- (y_i \log(\hat{y}_i) + (1 - y_i) \log(1 - \hat{y}_i)) \right] \quad (9)$$

where N is the number of historical samples, $y_i \in \{0, 1\}$ indicates the ground-truth anomaly label (1 for anomalous, 0 for normal), and $\hat{y}_i \in [0, 1]$ represents the predicted anomaly probability.

Subsequently, samples classified as normal are dynamically masked, whereas those flagged as anomalous are

forwarded to the localizer. The localizer optimizes the divergence between the predicted and actual root cause distributions via the following loss function:

$$\mathfrak{L}_2 = - \sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{s=1}^M c_{i,s} \log(p_{i,s}) \quad (10)$$

where M denotes the number of microservices; $c_{i,s} \in \{0, 1\}$ indicates whether microservice s is the true root cause for the i -th sample (1 for yes, 0 for no), and $p_{i,s}$ is the predicted probability that microservice s is the root cause. The overall joint loss function combines both objectives as follows:

$$\mathfrak{L} = \alpha \cdot \mathfrak{L}_1 + (1 - \alpha) \cdot \mathfrak{L}_2 \quad (11)$$

where α is a hyperparameter that balances the two loss terms.

Ultimately, the model produces a ranked list of candidate microservices based on their predicted root cause probabilities, prioritizing those most likely responsible for the anomaly.

5. Experiment

5.1. Datasets

We evaluate our model on two widely used open-source multimodal microservice benchmark systems, TrainTicket (TT) [34] and SocialNetwork(SN) [35]. These two systems are selected as benchmark platforms for the following reasons. First, both TrainTicket and SocialNetwork are widely used open-source benchmarks in the microservices research community [23, 24], which facilitates experimental reproducibility and enables fair comparisons with existing studies. Second, both systems contain relatively complete business logic and complex inter-service call relationships, allowing the generation of realistic logs, metrics, and traces that closely resemble those observed in real-world microservice environments.

TrainTicket simulates a railway ticketing system that supports ticket inquiry, booking, and payment, and has been widely adopted in prior studies. It consists of 41 microservices, among which 27 are business-related services. SocialNetwork represents a broadcast-style social networking platform where users can create, read, favorite, and repost content. It contains 21 microservices, including 12 business-related services.

For anomaly injection, the SocialNetwork system performs nine anomaly injections targeting different microservices (e.g., the home-timeline service and the media service) within each of four time periods, resulting in a total of 36 injections. Each anomaly lasts 2 minutes with a 30-second interval between consecutive injections. The injected anomaly types include CPU hog, network latency, and network packet loss. TrainTicket adopts a similar anomaly injection setup, performing a total of 81 anomaly injections across nine different time periods, targeting different microservices (e.g., assurance-service and price-service). Each anomaly lasts 10 minutes with a 2-minute interval, and the anomaly types are consistent with those used in SocialNetwork.

Table 2
Datasets information

Dataset	Anomaly type	Anomaly injection num	Microservice num	Sample size	Anomaly log template num	Metric type
SN	CPU_hog network_delay network_loss	36	21	98510	7	7
TT	CPU_hog network_delay network_loss	81	41	445584	60	7

From the log data, we extract 7 types of anomaly event templates for SocialNetwork, including 6 known anomaly templates and 1 unknown template. Unseen anomaly types are treated as unseen anomalies and grouped into a single event template. For TrainTicket, we extract 59 known anomaly templates plus 1 unseen anomaly template. For metric data in both datasets, we collect features across seven dimensions: `cpu_usage_system`, `cpu_usage_total`, `cpu_usage_user`, `memory_usage`, `memory_working_set`, `rx_bytes`, and `tx_bytes`.

Each trace consists of multiple spans representing a complete end-to-end request. Each span records critical information such as the frontend API name, the invoked microservice name and mapping ID, parent-child span relationships for constructing call-graph topology, operation start timestamps, and operation durations, from which we derive microservice call latency sequences.

We use the processed datasets provided by [23], which include 119,664 metrics, 94,365 logs, and 48,296 traces for SocialNetwork, and 2,007,801 metrics, 111,275 logs, and 126,384 traces for TrainTicket. After completing data preprocessing and temporal alignment across different modalities, we construct samples using a sliding-window strategy with a fixed sampling interval of 6 seconds. Specifically, for each continuous time segment, the original time series is first split into training and testing segments according to a 7:3 ratio. Sliding-window sampling is then applied independently to the training and testing segments, and the resulting samples are exclusively assigned to their corresponding sets.

Through this process, we obtain 98,510 samples for the SocialNetwork dataset and 445,584 samples for the TrainTicket dataset, while preserving similar anomaly ratios and root-cause distributions between the training and test sets. Table 2 presents the key information contained in the datasets.

5.2. Baselines

A) Anomaly Detection Baselines We compare MODIFY with 8 baseline methods for anomaly detection based on single-modal and multi-modal data.

- DeepLog (2017, ACM CCS)[3] is a classical log-index-based method, it performs anomaly detection by learning the sequential patterns of normal log sequences using an LSTM model and identifying anomalies based on deviations in the predicted probability of the next log entry.

- LogRobust (2019, ACM ESEC/FSE) [9] extracts semantic features from logs using FastText and TF-IDF, and employs an LSTM with an attention mechanism to identify abnormal log entries.

- MultimodalTrace (2019, IEEE CLOUD) [15] converts traces into span and response time series, employing a multimodal LSTM model to detect structural anomalies and response time anomalies.

- TraceAnomaly (2020, IEEE ISSRE) [16] performs anomaly detection tasks based on reconstruction probabilities from a Variational Autoencoder (VAE).

- DeepTraLog (2022, IEEE/ACM ICSE) [5] transforms dependencies between various services into graph structures, utilizing graph-based deep support vector machines for anomaly detection.

- TraceGra (2023, Computer Communications) [17] is an unsupervised encoder-decoder anomaly detection method that combines traces and performance metrics. It incorporates graph neural networks and long short-term memory networks to extract topological features and temporal features respectively for anomaly detection.

- Eadro (2023, IEEE/ACM ICSE) [23] models three modalities of data, feeds them into graph attention networks to construct global system representations for anomaly detection.

- AMuLSys (2025, Information Fusion) [25] adopts a hierarchical structure to simultaneously model three modalities of data, conducting anomaly detection through multi-layer contrastive learning.

B) Root Cause Localization Baselines For root cause localization, we compare MODIFY with 6 baseline models, including methods based on single-modal and multi-modal data.

- MonitorRank (2013, ACM SIGMETRICS) [12] generates invocation topology graphs between system instances and designs three fault-simulating walk strategies; when instances encounter anomalies, it localizes root causes using random walks on invocation graphs.

- CloudRanger (2018, IEEE/ACM CCGRID) [13] is a causality-graph-based method adopting a heuristic two-stage random walk strategy.

- DyCause (2021, ACM ISSTA) [14] identifies root causes of frontend performance anomalies using breadth-first strategies on constructed causality graphs.

- DeJaVu (2022, ACM ESEC/FSE) [6] is a feature extraction-based supervised learning method that uses GNNs to learn features and patterns from graph-structured data, demonstrating strong performance in fault diagnosis.

- Eadro (2023, IEEE/ACM ICSE) [23] emphasizes the connection between anomaly detection and root cause localization, enabling the model to assess system normality or rank potential root causes.

- MicroIRC (2024, Journal of Systems and Software) [18] proposes an instance-level root cause localization method for microservice systems, achieving fine-grained and dynamically adaptive fault localization.

5.3. Implementation

We conduct our experiments on a system equipped with an NVIDIA GeForce GTX 4060 GPU, running Windows 11 and Python 3.8. For hyperparameters, we set the hidden size of all fully connected layers to 64. Each Transformer encoder consists of two layers with four attention heads. Both the hidden size and fusion dimension in the GAT are set to 128, with a 4-head attention mechanism. To accelerate training, we configure each modality model with only one layer.

For the diffusion enhancement process, we set the number of diffusion noising steps to 100, with minimum and maximum noise ratios of 1×10^{-5} and 1×10^{-2} , respectively. We train MODIFY using the Adam optimizer with an initial learning rate of 0.001, a batch size of 256, and 70 training epochs. The hyperparameter α , which balances anomaly detection and root cause localization, is set to a default value of 0.5.

5.4. Evaluation Measurements

For anomaly detection, we adopt widely used binary classification metrics to evaluate model performance:

$$\text{Recall(Rec)} = \frac{\text{TP}}{\text{TP} + \text{FN}} \quad (12)$$

$$\text{Precision(Pre)} = \frac{\text{TP}}{\text{TP} + \text{FP}} \quad (13)$$

$$\text{F1-score(F1)} = \frac{2 \cdot \text{Precision} \cdot \text{Recall}}{\text{Precision} + \text{Recall}} \quad (14)$$

where TP denotes the number of successfully predicted anomalous samples, FP represents the number of normal samples incorrectly flagged as anomalies, TN is the number of correctly predicted normal samples, and FN indicates the number of anomalous samples misclassified as normal.

For root cause localization, we adopt two ranking-based evaluation metrics: top- k hit rate (HR@ k) [36] and top- k normalized discounted cumulative gain (NDCG@ k) [37].

$$\text{HR@}k = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N I\left(s_i^t \in S_{i,[1:k]}^p\right) \quad (15)$$

HR@ k measures the likelihood of identifying the true faulty microservice s_i^t appears in the top- k predicted candidates $S_{i,[1:k]}^p$, where N is the total number of test samples and $I(\cdot)$ is the indicator function.

$$\text{NDCG@}k = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{j=1}^M \frac{p_j}{\log_2(j+1)} \quad (16)$$

NDCG@ k evaluates the quality of the predicted ranking by assigning higher weights to correct predictions at higher ranks. Here, $p_{i,j} \in 0, 1$ indicates whether the j -th ranked microservice for the i -th sample is the true root cause.

We set $k = 1, 3, \text{ and } 5$ for performance evaluation. Since NDCG@1 is numerically equivalent to HR@1 in our setting, it is omitted from reporting.

5.5. Experimental Design

To thoroughly evaluate the effectiveness of MODIFY, we conduct extensive experiments covering comparative experiments, ablation studies, parameter sensitivity analysis, convergence analysis, time cost evaluation, and visualization, as summarized in Table 3.

5.6. Comparative Experiments

A) The Performance of Anomaly Detection To evaluate the performance of MODIFY in anomaly detection, we conduct comparative experiments against several baseline models. As shown in Table 4, MODIFY outperforms all baselines, achieving F1-scores of 0.925 on SocialNetwork and 0.841 on TrainTicket. DeepLog exhibits the weakest performance, with F1-scores of 0.385 and 0.240 on the two datasets, respectively, due to its reliance solely on log template index sequences while ignoring semantic content. In contrast, LogRobust extracts semantic features using the FastText algorithm and applies TF-IDF to aggregate word vectors. Its attention mechanism further emphasizes critical events during anomaly detection. As a result, LogRobust improves upon DeepLog by 0.5% and 2.5% in F1-score on SocialNetwork and TrainTicket, respectively. Trace-based anomaly detection methods generally achieve good results. MultimodalTrace analyzes textual labels and response times of normal traces using separate LSTM networks, while TraceAnomaly models invocation paths by encoding inter-service spans into trace vectors. These approaches achieve F1-scores of 0.486 and 0.472 on the TrainTicket dataset, respectively. However, such single-modal methods are notably outperformed by multimodal approaches that integrate multiple data sources, such as DeepTraLog and TraceGra.

DeepTraLog represents traces as graphs to preserve inter-service dependencies and integrates logs aligned with these traces. It uses GloVe to extract semantic features from logs and embeds them as span representations within the trace graph. As a result, DeepTraLog surpasses single-modal

Table 3

Summary of experimental design and evaluation metrics.

Experiment	Purpose	Evaluation Metrics
EX1 [4.6] Comparative Experiments	Verify the effectiveness of MODIFy in anomaly diagnose	Pre, Rec, F1-score, HR@k, NDCG@k ($k = 1/3/5$)
EX2 [4.7] Ablation Study	Verify the effectiveness of Transformer Encoder, Trace Diffusion Trunk, MSCA-CGFM and GAT	F1-score, HR@1, HR@5
EX3 [4.8] Parameter Sensitivity Analysis	Testing the influence of the number of diffusion steps, the quantity of multi-scale convolution kernels, the hyperparameters for balancing the detection and localization tasks, and the number of attention layers	F1-score, HR@1
EX4 [4.9] Convergence Analysis	Test the convergence performance of the MODIFy	Loss value
EX5 [4.10] Running Cost Analysis	Measure the training time and inference time per sample, as well as the GPU memory usage during model operation.	Time(sample/ms), GPU memory(GB)
EX6 [4.11] Statistical Significance Test	To verify whether the model results are statistically significant.	t-value, p-value
EX7 [4.12] Noise Resistance Test	Evaluate the model's robustness at different noise levels.	F1-score, HR@1
EX8 [4.13] Visualization	Intuitively display the effect of model anomaly diagnosis	None

Table 4

Performance comparison of anomaly detection.

Approaches	SocialNetWork			TrainTicket		
	F1	Pre	Rec	F1	Pre	Rec
DeepLog	0.385	0.396	0.374	0.240	0.287	0.206
LogRobust	0.390	0.332	0.472	0.265	0.193	0.421
TraceAnomaly	0.472	0.414	0.549	0.364	0.287	0.496
MultimodalTrace	0.486	0.408	0.602	0.429	0.329	0.617
DeepTraLog	0.700	0.796	0.624	0.596	0.614	0.579
TraceGra	0.749	0.708	0.795	0.682	0.652	0.714
AMuLSys	0.874	0.845	0.905	0.814	0.784	0.847
Eadro	0.904	0.909	0.900	0.834	0.825	0.844
Ours	0.925	0.914	0.937	0.841	0.860	0.824

methods like TraceAnomaly and LogRobust, improving F1-scores by more than 15%. Similarly, TraceGra models traces as structural graphs, combines them with metrics data, and employs VGAE and AE to extract structural and temporal features, respectively. The average F1 score across the two datasets exceeds 70%.

AMuLSys and Eadro, which leverage three data sources for anomaly detection, achieve exceptionally strong performance. AMuLSys effectively addresses class imbalance between normal and anomalous samples using an enhanced Mixup strategy. It further enables robust system state understanding through a multimodal hybrid graph representation combined with multilayer contrastive learning. As a result, it achieves F1-scores of 0.814 and 0.874 on the TrainTicket and SocialNetwork datasets, respectively.

Eadro demonstrates strong anomaly detection performance on both datasets by leveraging multimodal feature fusion, achieving an average F1 score of 0.869, which is very close to that of our model. However, MODIFy effectively captures long-range temporal dependencies across

microservices through Transformer encoders, thereby alleviating the information bottleneck caused by relying solely on one-dimensional causal convolutions. In addition, the introduced diffusion process further enhances trace representations, mitigating noise introduced by complex invocation chains and sparse request patterns, and significantly improving model robustness. Moreover, the enhanced multimodal fusion strategy enables MODIFy to capture fine-grained feature details at multiple scales, allowing it to consistently outperform Eadro across both datasets.

B) The Performance of Root Cause Localization In root cause localization, MODIFy consistently achieves the best overall performance across all evaluation metrics on both datasets, as shown in Table 5. Specifically, MODIFy attains an HR@1 of 0.878 on SocialNetwork and 0.816 on TrainTicket, significantly outperforming all baseline methods. Moreover, its NDCG@5 scores reach 0.921 and 0.917, respectively, indicating highly accurate and stable root cause ranking performance.

CloudRanger constructs causality graphs between instances and achieves relatively limited performance, with an HR@1 of 0.082 and NDCG@5 of 0.442 on SocialNetwork, and even lower results on TrainTicket. MonitorRank adopts a random walk strategy on topology graphs similar to CloudRanger and shows marginal improvements but still struggles to precisely localize root causes. DyCause identifies root causes using breadth-first search strategies on causality graphs, achieving an HR@5 of 0.581 on SocialNetwork and 0.424 on TrainTicket, demonstrating moderate localization capability.

DéjàVu trains fault-specific feature extractors and aggregates structural information from failure dependency graphs (FDGs) using attention mechanisms. By combining FDGs

Table 5

Performance comparison of Root cause localization.

Approaches	SocialNetWork					TrainTicket				
	HR@1	HR@3	HR@5	NDCG@3	NDCG@5	HR@1	HR@3	HR@5	NDCG@3	NDCG@5
CloudRanger	0.082	0.288	0.504	0.247	0.442	0.072	0.146	0.391	0.122	0.308
MonitorRank	0.109	0.197	0.473	0.165	0.375	0.076	0.125	0.332	0.099	0.256
DyCause	0.312	0.496	0.581	0.483	0.529	0.204	0.255	0.424	0.248	0.392
DejaVu	0.589	0.708	0.737	0.685	0.717	0.491	0.626	0.678	0.594	0.618
MicroIRC	0.759	0.864	0.928	0.827	0.884	0.704	0.822	0.904	0.755	0.878
Eadro	0.810	0.878	0.900	0.850	0.899	0.757	0.833	0.896	0.803	0.824
Ours	0.878	0.917	0.965	0.902	0.921	0.816	0.863	0.923	0.841	0.917

with graph neural networks, it achieves NDCG@5 scores of 0.717 on SocialNetwork and 0.618 on TrainTicket, indicating improved ranking quality. MicroIRC further integrates multi-dimensional monitoring indicators with temporal topology information, enabling fine-grained and dynamically adaptive fault localization. As a result, it achieves strong performance, with HR@5 exceeding 0.9 on both datasets and competitive NDCG@5 scores.

As root cause localization is inherently more complex than anomaly detection, multimodal approaches generally outperform single-modal methods. Eadro demonstrates strong localization capability by integrating multimodal features and jointly learning anomaly detection and root cause localization, achieving HR@1 scores of 0.810 on SocialNetwork and 0.757 on TrainTicket, and HR@3 values above 0.83 on both datasets. Nevertheless, MODIFY further enhances multimodal feature representation and interpretability through a multi-scale, channel-adaptive convolutional gated fusion mechanism, enabling more precise and robust identification of root causes under complex system dynamics.

5.7. Ablation study

To evaluate the advantages of multi-modal data and the effectiveness of MODIFY's individual modules, we design the following variants:

- MODIFY w/o t: excludes trace data from the multi-modal input.
- MODIFY w/o m: excludes metric data from the multi-modal input.
- MODIFY w/o l: excludes log data from the multi-modal input.
- MODIFY w/o TE: replaces Transformer encoders with 1D dilated causal convolutions to capture only local dependencies.
- MODIFY w/o DF: removes the diffusion enhancement module for trace features.
- MODIFY w/o DC: replaces the multi-scale channel-adaptive convolutional gating fusion module with a standard GLU gating mechanism.

As illustrated in Figure 5, the presence of multi-modal data is crucial for optimal model performance. Removing any single modality leads to a marked decrease in both HR@1 and F1-score. On the SocialNetwork dataset, the absence of any modality results in a 8.9%–19.2% drop

(a) SocialNetwork

(b) TrainTicket

Figure 5: Ablation experiments on two datasets

in HR@1 and a 10.1%–14.0% reduction in F1-score; on TrainTicket, HR@1 declines by 10.1%–19.3% and F1-score by 9.3%–14.7%. Notably, excluding trace data causes the most significant performance degradation, underscoring the importance of traces in capturing detailed execution paths and service interactions—information that logs and metrics alone cannot provide. Moreover, traces exhibit strong synergy with other modalities, and their removal disrupts this

Figure 6: Hyperparameter sensitivity analysis on two datasets. (a) Impact of diffusion step count; (b) Impact of multi-scale convolution kernel combinations; (c) Impact of the number of GAT layers; (d) Impact of the balance coefficient α .

complementary relationship, further diminishing diagnostic accuracy.

We also assess the impact of key architectural components through ablation studies. When Transformer encoders are replaced with dilated causal convolutions (MODIFY w/o TE), the model’s ability to capture long-range dependencies is weakened, resulting in average decreases of 0.8% in F1-score, 2.0% in HR@1, and 1.8% in HR@5. This demonstrates the value of Transformer encoders in modeling complex temporal and cross-metric relationships, thereby enriching semantic and contextual representations. Similarly, removing the diffusion enhancement module for trace features (MODIFY w/o DF) leads to an average drop of 3.5% in F1-score, 3.1% in HR@1, and 6.2% in HR@5, confirming that diffusion-based noise-resistant training enhances robustness by mitigating noise and feature drift in trace data.

Finally, eliminating the multi-scale channel-adaptive convolutional gating fusion module (MODIFY w/o DC) results in the most pronounced performance loss across both datasets. This module is essential for effective multi-modal feature integration, as it leverages multi-scale depthwise convolutions and adaptive channel reweighting to emphasize informative signals and suppress irrelevant noise. Together, these findings highlight the necessity of both multi-modal data and advanced fusion mechanisms for achieving reliable and accurate anomaly diagnosis in microservice systems.

5.8. Parameter Sensitivity Analysis

To assess the impact of diffusion enhancement on MODIFY’s robustness, we perform a hyperparameter sensitivity analysis on the number of diffusion steps using the SocialNetwork and TrainTicket. As shown in Figure 6(a), we evaluate step counts of 10, 50, 100, 300, 500, 1000. Results show that too few diffusion steps inject insufficient noise, limiting the model’s ability to learn robust features. Performance improves as the step count increases, peaking at 100 steps, where the model best captures true dependency patterns. Beyond this point, excessive noise degrades structural information in the traces, causing the model to learn noise rather than meaningful invocation patterns, which reduces effectiveness.

Simultaneously, to verify the effect of fusing features extracted by convolution kernels of different scales, we conduct a hyperparameter sensitivity analysis on multi-scale fused features using kernel combinations of 3×3 ; 3×3 and

Figure 7: Convergence curve for SocialNetwork and TrainTicket

5×5 ; 3×3 , 5×5 , and 7×7 ; and 3×3 , 5×5 , 7×7 , and 9×9 on the SocialNetwork dataset. As shown in Figure 6(b), the model achieves optimal performance when fusing features from parallel 3×3 and 5×5 convolutions. The 3×3 kernel, with its smaller receptive field, captures local details effectively, while the 5×5 kernel captures broader contextual information. Their combination enables complementary multi-level feature extraction. In contrast, 7×7 and 9×9 kernels have excessively large receptive fields, which may introduce sparsity and lead to sparser, less detailed feature representations, causing loss of local detail. Additionally, fusing too many scales significantly increases computational cost without corresponding performance gains.

We also analyze the impact of GAT layer depth on model performance. As shown in Figure 6(c), we evaluate 1, 2, 3, and 4 GAT layers. Increasing the depth from 1 to 2 slightly improves HR@1 and F1-score, as deeper layers capture more complex dependencies. However, performance declines beyond 2 layers, likely due to over-smoothing and increased optimization difficulty, which weaken feature discrimination. Given the marginal gain from using two layers, we adopt a single GAT layer to improve training efficiency.

Finally, we perform a hyperparameter sensitivity analysis on the balance coefficient α , which controls the trade-off between anomaly detection and root cause localization. As shown in Figure 6(d), we test α values from 0.1 to 0.9. The model achieves optimal performance at $\alpha = 0.5$, suggesting that equal emphasis on both tasks yields the best results. In contrast, overly small or large α values lead to task imbalance and degraded performance.

Table 6

Comparison of training time, inference time (ms/sample), and GPU memory usage (GB) for different methods on SocialNetwork and TrainTicket.

Method	SocialNetwork			TrainTicket		
	Train Time	Inference Time	GPU Mem	Train Time	Inference Time	GPU Mem
CloudRanger	85.841	0.265	0.087	106.582	0.782	0.147
DyCause	126.584	0.542	0.221	158.724	1.086	0.497
MonitorRank	138.671	1.227	0.433	251.883	1.603	0.673
MicroIRC	309.756	4.687	0.710	372.147	4.982	1.249
Eadro	148.298	1.414	0.754	261.688	1.759	1.376
AMuLSys	406.744	3.944	1.268	475.414	5.013	2.898
MODIFy	156.482	1.578	0.899	265.469	1.872	2.011

5.9. Convergence Analysis

We evaluate the convergence of MODIFy, as shown in Figure 7. The training loss consistently decreases on both the SocialNetwork and TrainTicket datasets, indicating stable convergence. On SocialNetwork, the loss drops sharply within the first 10 epochs and then stabilizes with minor fluctuations, suggesting that the model quickly captures key data patterns. On TrainTicket, the initial loss is slightly lower and follows a similar trend, with a rapid decline in the early epochs followed by a gradual decrease, maintaining a low level throughout. Neither curve exhibits signs of overfitting or oscillation, demonstrating that MODIFy maintains strong training stability and generalization across datasets of varying scale and complexity.

5.10. Running Cost Analysis

To highlight the advantages of MODIFy in jointly training the two-stage tasks, we evaluate its training time, inference time, and GPU memory consumption on both the SocialNetwork and TrainTicket datasets. For fair comparison, the per-sample training and inference times are obtained by averaging the time cost over all epochs.

As shown in Table 6, apart from rule-based or traditional machine learning single-task methods such as CloudRanger, DyCause, and MonitorRank, MODIFy achieves lower training and inference latency on both datasets compared with other single-task deep learning approaches, including MicroIRC and AMuLSys, and is only slightly slower than Eadro, which also adopts joint learning for two tasks. On the SocialNetwork dataset, the per-sample training and inference times of MODIFy are 156.482 ms and 1.578 ms, respectively. On the more complex TrainTicket dataset, these times increase moderately to 265.469 ms and 1.872 ms. This advantage mainly stems from the reuse of fused representations learned after the graph attention network, which avoids independently and repeatedly processing raw data for two separate tasks in a two-stage pipeline, thereby reducing unnecessary computational overhead. In addition, MODIFy applies efficiency-oriented optimizations to computationally intensive components: the graph attention network is restricted to a single layer to balance performance and training cost (as indicated by the hyperparameter sensitivity analysis), and the denoising network in the diffusion module

adopts a lightweight yet effective architecture composed of stacked one-dimensional convolutional layers with ReLU activations. These design choices effectively reduce time complexity while maintaining strong representational capacity.

In addition to per-sample inference latency, we further evaluate the overhead of full offline retraining, which is necessary when service dependency structures evolve due to deployment updates or scaling operations. On the SocialNetwork dataset, complete retraining requires approximately 40 minutes, while on TrainTicket it requires about 3 hours under the same hardware configuration. These results indicate that periodic retraining is practical for most production-level microservice systems.

In terms of space complexity, due to the incorporation of computationally intensive components such as Transformer encoders, graph attention networks, and diffusion models, MODIFy inevitably incurs higher GPU memory consumption (0.899 GB on SocialNetwork and 2.011 GB on TrainTicket), offering no clear advantage over other baseline methods in this regard. However, MODIFy trades a moderate increase in GPU memory usage for substantial reductions in training and inference time, achieving an effective balance between model complexity and diagnostic performance. This makes MODIFy particularly well suited for large-scale and latency-sensitive microservice environments, where fast and reliable anomaly diagnosis is critical.

5.11. Statistical Significance Test

To examine whether the performance improvements of MODIFy over strong baselines are statistically significant rather than incidental, we conduct paired statistical significance tests between MODIFy and its closest competitor, Eadro, on both the SocialNetwork and TrainTicket datasets.

Specifically, we perform a two-tailed paired t-test under identical experimental settings. For each method, we run 10 independent trials using the same experimental configuration and random seed control, and record the corresponding performance metrics. For each trial, the performance difference between MODIFy and Eadro is computed, forming a set of paired differences.

Let d_i denote the performance difference of the i -th paired experiment, and \bar{d} represent the mean of all paired

(a) SocialNetwork: Left(MODIFy), Right(Eadro)

(b) TrainTicket: Left(MODIFy), Right(Eadro)

Figure 8: Different methods' robustness analysis on two datasets.

Table 7

Statistical Significance Test Results

Metric	Method	SocialNetWork		TrainTicket			
		Mean \pm Std	t-value	p-value	Mean \pm Std	t-value	p-value
F1	MODIFy	0.925 \pm 0.009	3.854	0.004	0.842 \pm 0.004	4.256	0.002
	Eadro	0.904 \pm 0.009			0.834 \pm 0.006		
HR@1	MODIFy	0.877 \pm 0.013	4.612	0.001	0.816 \pm 0.006	3.987	0.003
	Eadro	0.810 \pm 0.026			0.757 \pm 0.047		

differences, which reflects the average performance gain of MODIFy over Eadro. Let \bar{d} represent the mean of all paired differences, which reflects the average performance gain of MODIFy over Eadro. Let s_d denote the standard deviation of these paired differences, measuring the variability of the performance gap across different runs, and n be the number of paired samples. The t-statistic is calculated as:

$$t = \frac{\bar{d}}{s_d / \sqrt{n}} \quad (17)$$

This formulation normalizes the mean performance difference by its estimated standard error, thereby quantifying how confidently the observed improvement deviates from zero. A larger t-value indicates stronger evidence that the performance gain is systematic rather than caused by random fluctuations.

With a sample size of $n = 10$ and a confidence level of $p = 0.05$, the corresponding critical t-value is 2.228, as determined from the t-distribution table. When the computed t-value exceeds this threshold, the observed difference between MODIFy and Eadro is considered statistically significant.

Table 7 summarizes the results of the statistical significance tests. As shown, MODIFy consistently outperforms Eadro with statistically significant margins on both tasks. On the SocialNetwork dataset, MODIFy achieves an average t-value of 4.233 with a corresponding average p-value of 0.0026. Similarly, on the TrainTicket dataset, the average t-value reaches 4.122, and the average p-value is 0.0027.

Overall, all reported t-values exceed the critical threshold, and the corresponding p-values are well below 0.05, confirming that the performance improvements of MODIFy over Eadro in both anomaly detection and root cause localization are statistically significant. These results indicate that the observed performance advantages are robust and

consistently reproducible, rather than arising from random fluctuations.

5.12. Noise Resistance Test

To evaluate the robustness of MODIFy under noisy conditions, we conduct noise injection experiments on the SocialNetwork and TrainTicket datasets by progressively increasing the noise level in the test sets and examining the resulting model performance. Figure 8 illustrates how MODIFy and Eadro perform as noise intensity increases, evaluated on both anomaly detection and root cause localization.

Overall, MODIFy demonstrates consistently stronger robustness than Eadro across both datasets and evaluation metrics. Under low noise levels, MODIFy maintains relatively stable diagnostic performance. As the noise level increases, its performance degrades in a gradual and smooth manner, and even under severe noise interference, MODIFy is able to preserve high F1 and HR@1 scores. In contrast, Eadro suffers from a much sharper performance degradation. This robustness advantage is particularly pronounced on the TrainTicket dataset, which features more complex service invocation structures and sparser trace data distributions.

The superior robustness of MODIFy can be largely attributed to its diffusion-enhanced trace modeling mechanism, which enables the model to capture intrinsic anomaly propagation patterns rather than overfitting to noise or transient fluctuations. Moreover, the joint anomaly detection and root cause localization framework allows diffusion-enhanced and fused representations to be shared across tasks, effectively mitigating the error accumulation commonly observed in traditional two-stage pipeline approaches and further strengthening overall robustness.

5.13. Visualization

To intuitively demonstrate the anomaly diagnosis effectiveness of our model, we use t-SNE [38] to visualize the representations learned by MODIFy and its variants for identifying anomalous microservices, as shown in Figure 9.

Figure 9(a) shows that MODIFy produces well-separated, compact clusters with clear category boundaries, indicating strong discriminative power for effective anomaly localization. In contrast, removing the multi-scale channel-adaptive convolutional gating module (Figure 9(b) w/o DC) or the diffusion enhancement module (Figure 9(c) w/o DF) causes the feature space to become less structured, with overlapping

Figure 9: Representations learned by MODIFY and its variants.

clusters, blurred boundaries, and weakened category separation, reflecting a decline in discriminative power. Further, removing any input modalities such as trace (Figure 9(d) w/o t), metric (Figure 9(e) w/o m), or log (Figure 9(f) w/o l) reduces feature compactness and increases class overlap. Notably, excluding trace data causes significant cluster mixing and a sharp drop in discriminative ability, consistent with our ablation findings.

These visualizations confirm that multimodal feature fusion and key architectural modules are critical for learning a well-structured, discriminative feature space. The full MODIFY model excels in distinguishing anomalous microservices, while removing any core component degrades its diagnostic performance.

6. Threats to Validity

Based on the theory of experimentation in software engineering [39], we analyze the threats to validity of our framework from the following aspects: construct, internal, conclusion, and external validity.

Construct threat mainly lies in the selection of hyperparameters and evaluation metrics. In our experiments, we carefully tune key hyperparameters such as the number of diffusion steps, the number of convolution kernels, and the balance coefficient α between anomaly detection and root cause localization. We also adopt widely used evaluation metrics, including F1-score, HR@ k , and NDCG@ k , to ensure the reliability and comparability of our results.

However, there is still a possibility that other hyperparameter settings or alternative metrics may affect the final performance.

Internal threat primarily concern the implementation correctness of the proposed framework and the reliability of the experimental process. To mitigate these threats, we rely on open-source libraries and conduct multiple rounds of code review and testing to reduce potential implementation errors. All experiments are repeated multiple times to ensure result stability and reproducibility. In addition, potential internal threats may arise from the scale of logs, metrics, and traces, as variations in data volume and microservice system complexity (e.g., service scale and dependency structure) could influence the observed diagnostic performance.

In this study, we conduct experiments on two representative microservice benchmark systems with substantially different scales and complexities. Specifically, SocialNetwork consists of 21 microservices with approximately 98,510 samples, while TrainTicket includes 41 microservices and 445,584 samples. Notably, although TrainTicket has a significantly larger data volume and service scale, its overall diagnostic performance is not consistently superior to that on SocialNetwork. This observation suggests that model performance is not dominated by data scale alone, and that microservice system complexity, such as the number of services, deeper dependency chains, and more heterogeneous service interactions, plays a more important role in affecting diagnostic effectiveness.

Furthermore, our analysis does not rely on the raw data volume of any single modality. Instead, we extract anomalous log event templates rather than raw log frequencies, represent metrics using statistical features across multiple resource and network dimensions, and focus on end-to-end latency patterns and invocation relationships in trace data. As a result, our conclusions are primarily derived from consistent cross-modal behavioral patterns, rather than the absolute scale of any individual data source. Although consistent trends are observed across systems with markedly different data scales and invocation complexities, we acknowledge that in much larger systems or under different sampling strategies, additional behaviors may emerge that are not fully captured by the current evaluation.

External threat is associated with the generalization of our framework to other microservice systems and deployment environments. A potential threat to external validity lies in the assumption of a static microservice dependency graph. In this study, the service dependency graph is constructed during the data preprocessing stage based on historical invocation traces. Since the set of microservices in the benchmark datasets is fixed and known, the node set and edge set are explicitly defined to represent service-level dependencies. This design aligns with the evaluation setting but may limit the applicability of MODIFY to real-world microservice systems with highly dynamic topologies.

To mitigate this issue in practical deployments, the service dependency graph can be maintained through periodic incremental updates. Specifically, edges and their weights can be updated based on invocation statistics within a recent trace window, while an expiration mechanism can be applied to remove long-unused dependencies. Newly emerged service nodes can be incorporated into the graph by initializing their representations using multimodal features, followed by lightweight online updates. Since such updates may require periodic retraining or representation refresh, we evaluated the feasibility of offline retraining. On a single GPU, a complete training takes approximately 40 minutes (0.899 GB GPU memory) on SocialNetwork and about 3 hours (2.011 GB GPU memory) on TrainTicket. These overheads are practical for production environments where models are updated weekly or monthly, suggesting that periodic graph and model updates are feasible in real-world systems.

Conclusion threat relates to the generalizability of our experimental findings. Our evaluation is conducted on two widely used public microservice datasets, TrainTicket and SocialNetwork, which cover common anomaly types studied in prior work, including CPU hogs, network delay, and packet loss. We present detailed anomaly diagnosis results for each anomaly type and provide ablation studies and sensitivity analyses to further support our conclusions.

Benchmark datasets cannot fully reflect the diversity and scale of real-world microservice environments, and rare or highly complex anomaly scenarios may therefore be underrepresented in our evaluation. As a supervised learning based approach, MODIFY's detection capability is influenced by the anomaly types present in the training data,

although it can still generalize to unseen anomalies as long as they manifest as abnormal patterns in runtime observables such as logs, metrics, and traces. In practice, a common strategy in large-scale systems is to combine unsupervised methods with human expertise, where unsupervised models generate coarse-grained pseudo-labels that are refined by engineers and then used to train supervised diagnostic models. Under such semi-supervised or human-in-the-loop settings, MODIFY remains practically applicable and effective.

For root cause localization, MODIFY focuses on service-level localization by identifying the microservice responsible for observed anomalies and therefore does not support finer-grained diagnosis, such as instance-level or container-level root causes. Its detection capability depends on observable runtime signals from traces, metrics, and application logs, meaning that anomalies without clear manifestations in these modalities may go undetected. For instance, infrastructure-level issues such as control-plane scheduling anomalies may not be captured if they do not result in noticeable service-level latency changes, resource contention, or abnormal log patterns, and such components are also outside the scope of the microservice invocation dependency graph. In real-world scenarios where anomalies often arise from multiple interacting factors, MODIFY outputs a probability distribution over all microservices and provides a ranked list of candidate root causes, allowing multiple services to receive high scores and be jointly considered by operators. However, existing benchmarks typically annotate each anomaly with a single primary root cause, making the systematic evaluation of multi-root scenarios difficult. Therefore, addressing multi-root anomalies and enabling finer-grained localization needs to be explored more in the future.

7. Conclusion and Future Work

This paper presents a unified multimodal anomaly diagnosis framework, MODIFY, based on multimodal feature fusion and diffusion enhancement, effectively addressing diagnostic challenges in microservice architectures arising from dynamic topologies, complex service dependencies, and heterogeneous multimodal data characteristics. Through the synergistic fusion of logs, metrics, and traces, MODIFY introduces a multi-scale channel-adaptive convolutional gating fusion module, significantly alleviating the semantic association limitations inherent in traditional linear fusion strategies.

To mitigate severe noise interference in trace data, we propose a diffusion-based noise-resilient training mechanism that injects controllable noise into trace features and employs denoising objectives to improve robustness against disrupted anomaly propagation paths. In addition, a multi-scale Convolutional Gated Linear Unit (CGLU) and a channel-adaptive weighting mechanism are designed to dynamically balance multimodal features across different temporal and semantic scales. Furthermore, Graph Attention Networks are incorporated to capture inter-service dependencies, enabling a unified diagnostic architecture that

jointly performs anomaly detection and service-level root cause localization, thereby avoiding the noise amplification commonly observed in conventional sequential workflows.

From a practical perspective, MODIFY is designed to provide interpretable diagnostic outputs by explicitly associating detection and localization results with observable signals that system operators are already familiar with, such as anomalous log event templates, changes in resource or network-related metric dimensions, and concrete service invocation paths and end-to-end latency patterns in traces. These modality-aligned signals offer intuitive diagnostic cues that can be readily integrated into daily operational workflows. However, since the current framework focuses on service-level localization, it does not yet provide fine-grained explanations at the instance or container level, which remains an important direction for further investigation.

We conduct experiments on the SocialNetwork and TrainTicket benchmarks to demonstrate the effectiveness of MODIFY. Results show that it achieves an average F1-score of 0.883 and HR@1 of 0.847, significantly outperforming state-of-the-art methods. Ablation studies further confirm the critical roles of multimodal data synergy, diffusion-based noise resilience, and multi-scale fusion modules in performance improvement.

Our future work will explore lightweight deployment strategies of MODIFY in production-like environments, such as elastic cloud deployments, to better satisfy real-time operational requirements while reducing computational overhead. We also plan to design topology-adaptive mechanisms to handle highly dynamic microservice orchestration environments. In particular, while MODIFY effectively models complex multi-modal dependencies under a fixed topology assumption, more native support for dynamic microservice topologies remains an important direction for future work. In real-world cloud environments, service dependencies may evolve due to scaling operations, deployment updates, or transient failures. Incorporating mechanisms such as online learning of adjacency relationships or event-driven update strategies that automatically trigger localized topology updates could enable the model to adapt more promptly to structural changes, further improving its applicability in highly dynamic production systems. In addition, we will investigate the integration of multimodal large language models to enhance the interpretability of microservice anomaly diagnosis, enabling more human-centered and interactive diagnostic support for system operators.

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